

DEVELOPMENT OF STUDENTS' CRIMINAL EMOTIONAL-CIVIC COMPETENCES BASED ON THE "GIVE ME THE WORD" METHOD IN MOTHER LANGUAGE LESSONS

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The role of mother tongue education in a person's rightful place in society is incomparable. Mother tongue is the main tool that shows the development, maturity, upbringing, and maturity of human intelligence and leads to these levels. A person understands and accepts everything through language as long as he lives. The goal of today's education is to educate a student who is adaptable to the constantly changing world, who can critically analyze every situation, and who can freely, confidently, and clearly express his personal attitude to every reality.

The equal formation of basic and subject-related competencies in educational processes, in particular, the development of students' socio-emotional and civic competence through mother tongue education, is the basis for educating the hero of today's time, the model of a student in demand in today's world.

Social-emotional and civic competence includes skills and abilities that play an important role in various social relationships, personal development, and active participation in society throughout a person's life. This competence is manifested through aspects such as self-awareness, communication with others, managing emotions, understanding social responsibility, and active participation in civic activities. We found it necessary to show and explain the components of this competence as follows.

1. Self-awareness
2. Self-management
3. Empathy
4. Social awareness
5. Relationship skills
6. Responsible decision-making
7. Civic responsibility
8. Cultural and global skills
9. Social responsibility

Self-awareness: This is the ability to understand one's own feelings, values, strengths and weaknesses. A person must understand their own

emotional state, be aware of their own characteristics and know how to manage them.

Self-management: This is the ability to effectively manage one's own feelings, actions and time. This component includes managing stress, being disciplined to achieve goals, being self-motivated and being emotionally stable.

Empathy: The ability to understand and empathise with the feelings, needs and perspectives of others. Empathy helps to appreciate and relate to the diversity of people.

Social awareness (understanding social norms and rules): Understanding and following the norms, rules and cultural aspects accepted in society. This component helps a person to be flexible in a social environment.

Relationship skills. Effective Communication: The ability to communicate clearly, openly, and respectfully. This includes listening, expressing one's thoughts clearly, and resolving misunderstandings. Collaboration: The ability to work with others, work effectively in a group, and work together to achieve common goals. Relationship Management: The ability to maintain good interpersonal relationships, resolve conflict, and strengthen social bonds.

Responsible decision making. Ethical and socially responsible decision making: This component includes an individual's ability to understand the social, ethical, and legal consequences of their decisions and to make decisions that are consistent with them. Problem Solving: The ability to find solutions to complex situations, consider different options, and choose the best solution.

Civic responsibility. Active Participation in Society: Actively participating as a citizen in the social, political, and economic life of society. This includes voting in elections, maintaining public order, and participating in social projects. Legal literacy: Understanding citizenship rights and responsibilities, knowledge of laws and their application.

Cultural and global skills. Promoting social justice and equity: Striving to promote justice, equality and human rights in society. This component includes a critical assessment of discrimination, prejudice and unfair treatment. Appreciation of cultural diversity: The ability to understand and appreciate different cultures, traditions and values. This component helps a person to function successfully in a global world.

Social responsibility. Understanding global issues: Having knowledge about global issues in the world (such as climate change, poverty, migration) and being willing to contribute to solving them. Responsibility towards society and the environment: This component requires an understanding of the impact

of one's actions on society and the environment and acting in accordance with them. This includes aspects such as protecting the environment, supporting social justice, and helping others.

Thus, socio-emotional and civic competences encompass the basic skills and abilities necessary for a person to be successful in his personal and social life. They help to develop aspects such as self-awareness, effective communication with others, understanding of social responsibility, and active participation in society. By developing this competence, students can achieve success not only in their personal lives, but also in social and professional spheres. Therefore, special attention should be paid to developing this competence in students by forming their skills related to this competence in the process of mother tongue education.

We observed the extent to which the above-mentioned components of competence were formed in students during the pilot lessons. According to the results of the first pilot lesson, although they did not fully reflect the components of the competence they were aiming to develop, they showed efforts to behave freely in public, treat others with respect, and freely express their personal thoughts and opinions. However, they encountered certain difficulties in questions and tasks that form skills related to self-confidence, correct assessment of the situation, decision-making, expression of feelings, critical and analytical thinking, and understanding of rights and obligations. Therefore, we tried to develop the following methodological recommendations in accordance with the development of the components of the competence that students need to develop. The following method serves to develop students' social-emotional citizenship competencies in native language education:

"Give me the floor" method (in the form of discussion and discuss)

Students' independent thinking, ability to freely express their personal opinions in public, react to reality, and critically analyze social and emotional citizenship competencies are formed.

1. A video, audio, or text is presented or a question is posed for discussion or reaction. Students are given time to read, listen, and prepare.

2. After the students have familiarized themselves with the materials provided, each student is given a sheet to write their personal opinion and reaction. They must write an opinion consisting of 3 sentences. And a time is set for writing their opinion.

3. Time is given to express the opinion in a clear and concise form, and each student must reduce their opinion consisting of 3 sentences to a clear, short, and concise form in the form of 1 sentence.

4. The teacher asks the students to read the final version of their personal opinions in turn. The students ask permission to express their opinions by saying, "Give me the floor." The teacher gives permission for the student to express his/her opinion, and at that moment the opposing parties write down whose opinion they disagree with. The opinion of each student in the class is listened to in turn. Each student listens to the opinions of his/her classmates and writes down if he/she disagrees, and if he/she agrees, he/she supports.

5. After everyone's opinions have been listened to, the teacher determines the general attitude of the students in the class to the opinions listened to. That is, the opinions given by the students in the class are considered to be in agreement and disagreement. The results are written on the board for each student to see and reflect on. For example, Mehrinoz is against the opinion of 21 students, but agrees with 9, Hikmatillo is against 15 opinions, and agrees with 15 opinions. In total, 36 agree and 24 disagree.

It can be seen from the figures that if everyone in society has their own personal opinion and views, a conflict of opinions will arise. From the agreement of opinions, by agreeing on the best idea, society will grow and develop. Opposing shallow opinions will save society.

The purpose of this technology is to help students develop the skills of expressing reactions and critical analysis.

In conclusion, it can be said that independent and creative, critical and analytical thinking, decision-making, respecting the decisions of others, communication, as well as socio-emotional competencies are very important for students. These are the most necessary skills for a person to take his place in society and state life. A person who has these skills will take his place in the family, neighborhood, and society. He will actively participate in state affairs. He will try to renew himself, those around him, and the life of society. We can easily achieve such a responsible task in the process of mother tongue education by implementing educational technologies such as the above into the lesson processes.

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